

Enabling Workflow Performance Evaluation for Galaxy via Automated Benchmarking

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Abstract—As a science gateway grows, in terms of the number of users, number of jobs it handles, diversity of the workload, or number of installations, it becomes increasingly important to focus on efficiency. Efficiency helps make better use of available resources and hence better support users. Here we describe a benchmarking automation framework for the Galaxy science gateway platform that helps evaluate tool, workflow, and system performance. The framework, named ABM for Automated Benchmarking, allows users to easily benchmark and compare workflow runtimes on different Galaxy deployments as well as evaluate tool’s performance using different resource configurations. Here we describe the ABM design, implementation details, and showcase its use in three difference usage scenarios.

Index Terms—Galaxy, benchmark automation, cloud

I. INTRODUCTION

Evaluating the performance of software tools and scientific workflows is crucial for end-users, tool developers, and system administrators. End-users need to estimate runtimes, costs, and compare performance across providers. Tool and workflow developers benchmark to optimize performance. Administrators evaluate for capacity planning and performance tuning. However, comprehensive performance evaluation is often time-consuming and nuanced, involving running tools with varying resource allocations, input parameters, and on different systems. For workflows, additional steps like tool installation and reconfiguration are required. Collecting and interpreting such performance data is complex, and therefore often overlooked, leading to sub-optimal user experience or system under-utilization.

We present Automated Benchmarking (ABM), a command-line tool that automates and tracks the benchmarking process of tools and workflows for Galaxy - a popular biomedical data analysis and workflow management platform [4]. Galaxy supports thousands of domain-specific tools and workflows, with public servers accommodating over 10,000 active monthly users and processing approximately two million jobs each month. Galaxy can also be launched on the cloud [7] or installed on local hardware. This scale and heterogeneity of uses necessitates performance optimization and cross-provider comparisons, motivating ABM’s development. Other efforts, such as JUBE [6] and Hummingbird [2], are alternative benchmarking frameworks, but they lack support for Galaxy.

ABM enables comprehensive tool and workflow performance evaluation by automating the benchmarking process

on any Galaxy installation, helping users better understand and optimize their usage. It handles uploading of workflows and input data, installing missing tools, running specified benchmark configurations, monitoring workload execution, and collecting runtime data. ABM uses descriptor files to simplify the definition of complex experiments. This approach also ensures consistent and repeatable benchmarking. We have used ABM to benchmark various analyses, demonstrating significant cloud cost reductions (40-80%) through identified configuration changes [1].

We envision ABM adoption during tool/workflow publishing, ensuring operational readiness, providing runtime estimates, and optimizing default resource configurations. In this paper, we describe ABM’s capabilities, implementation, and usage, concluding with lessons learned and future enhancement ideas.

II. AN OVERVIEW OF ABM

ABM enables users to run workflows, configure cloud compute resources, and collect job runtime metrics in an automated bulk fashion, thereby simplifying and accelerating the benchmarking process required for performance evaluation. ABM is implemented in Python with a focus on ease of use, scripting, and integration. It leverages BioBlend [8] and Planemo [3] to interact with the Galaxy platform (**Fig. 1**). ABM also includes mechanisms to monitor and manage the status of jobs, providing real-time feedback, job re-submission, and logs to users. ABM can be installed directly from PyPI and the source code is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/galaxyproject/gxabm>), where users can find documentation, access the latest updates, and contribute to development.

Interaction with ABM is managed via YAML-based configuration files that capture all the benchmarking steps while allowing users to define evaluation settings in a human-readable and editable format. This approach also allows details of each benchmark to be precisely captured, tracked, and easily shared. A sample set of definitions is shown in (**Fig. 2**) (for complete configuration details see the ABM documentation). The configuration files have a three-tier structure. The highest conceptual level is an *Experiment*. Each Experiment consists of one or more *Benchmarks* and each Benchmark consists of one or more *Workflows* and *Input Datasets*. The Experiment

Fig. 1. Evaluation system design for ABM. ABM leverages existing libraries to interact with Galaxy and collect benchmark data. ABM can also reconfigure Galaxy to broaden the benchmarking space.

defines how many times each Benchmark should be run, which resources to use, and an optional set of resource configuration rules to iterate over. Each configuration rule defines the number of CPUs and amount of memory a tool should use. The Benchmark specifies input and output details for the Workflow, such as dataset and history names, and matches inputs from a Galaxy workflow submission form (Fig. 3). Workflow and Input Dataset definitions point to where those objects can be downloaded from.

A key advantage of using ABM to run workflows on several Galaxy servers is that users are able to use the human readable names for datasets, histories, and workflows. For security reasons, Galaxy represents these objects using ID values that are unique to a Galaxy instance. These ID values are used when interacting with the Galaxy server through the REST API. However, this presents problems when users want to run the same workload on several different Galaxy servers. ABM handles this translation from human readable name to the Galaxy ID, significantly reducing the setup and configuration time needed to perform benchmarking experiments.

III. USE CASES

In this section we present three sample use cases that each showcase ABM’s utility for a different user persona. The first use case focuses on end users, allowing them to compare runtime characteristics of a workflow and performance of different Galaxy servers. The second use case focuses on tool or workflow developers and demonstrates how ABM can be used to benchmark workflow’s execution as part of continuous integration. The third use case focuses on systems administrators, showcasing how to benchmark different cloud resource configurations.

A. Evaluate Workflow Performance on Different Servers

Currently there are more than 150 public Galaxy servers where various groups and institutions have set up a server

```

---
# Experiment definition
name: Variant-Analyses
runs: 3
benchmark_confs:
  - benchmarks/vc.yml
cloud:
  - australia
  - usa
---
# Benchmark definition
- output_history_base_name: Variant-Calling
  workflow_id: Generic variation analysis on WGS PE
  data
  runs:
    - history_name: 2GB
      inputs:
        - name: Paired Collection
          collection: Subsample of reads from
            SRR24043307
        - name: GenBank genome
          dataset_id: GRCh38.p14.gbff.gz
        - name: Name for genome database
          value: h38
---
# Workflows definition
variant: https://benchmarking-inputs.s3.amazonaws.com/vc-iwc.ga

```

Fig. 2. A sample definition for an Experiment, a Benchmark, and a Workflow. The Experiment definition specifies some metadata, which Benchmark file to use, on which resources to run the Benchmark, and what job configurations should be used (job configurations require administrative privileges to use and are not shown here). The Benchmark definition specifies the Workflow and Input Dataset information. The Workflow definition specifies an online location of the Galaxy workflow file that ABM will import into the relevant Galaxy server. Input Datasets are defined in the same fashion as Workflows, but no example is shown. For a complete example, see <https://github.com/SchatzLabJHU/abm-examples>.

Fig. 3. The variant analysis workflow configuration form on the Galaxy server. The values and labels seen in the Galaxy interface are the same as the keys and values used in the Benchmark configuration file.

either as a public resource or a way to expose their tools: <https://galaxyproject.org/use/>. Within these servers there is a subset of servers known as *usegalaxy**. These are general purpose, national Galaxy servers that cater to a wide user audience. Across all these servers there are many differences. These include systemic differences such as system capabilities, proximity to data, and legal jurisdiction. The differences also include configuration differences, such as which tools are

installed or how many resources those tools are configured to use. With many choices, service users often want to know which servers can run their workloads and which one perform best. Evaluating those servers is a time-consuming task requiring the user to transfer data and workflows as well as invoke and monitor job invocations. Here we showcase how ABM can be used to simply perform server comparison.

```
australia:
  url: https://usegalaxy.org.au
  key: ***User's Galaxy AU API key***
usa:
  url: https://usegalaxy.org
  key: ***User's Galaxy US API key***
```

Fig. 4. Example ABM profile configuration pointing to two Galaxy servers and letting ABM know how to access those servers. This is a global system configuration file that contains links to any number of servers.

Running the performance benchmarks requires us to set up the ABM configuration with the target servers. **Fig. 4** shows a sample configuration pointing to the Australian and US usegalaxy servers. With the necessary configuration available, we can invoke ABM to run a workflow on those servers:

```
#!/usr/bin/env bash
for server in australia usa ; do
  abm $server workflow import variant
  abm $server history import variant-2g
done
abm experiment run experiments/vc.yml
abm experiment summarize --markdown metrics/Variants-Analysis
```

The script uploads a workflow and input data to the given Galaxy servers. Then the experiment is run (Experiment definition in **Fig. 2**). The source locations of the supplied workflow and input data objects from where they are uploaded to Galaxy are defined in their respective configuration files (not shown). Once submitted, ABM will monitor workflow execution and upon completion of all workflow jobs, ABM will retrieve runtime characteristics and summarize the results. A snippet of results is shown in **Table I**, capturing runtime characteristics of each tool in the workflow. The data shown in the table is a very condensed version of what the `history summarize` command returns to make it fit the paper format. The full results returned include run ID, server, tool resource configuration, workflow name, Galaxy history name, inputs, tool ID, tool version, job state, number of CPUs allocated, amount of memory allocated, job runtime, number of CPUs used, memory limit, and maximum memory usage. The output from this command can be saved to a CSV file for downstream analysis or a more compact Markdown format for a human readable overview.

As can be seen, with ABM, once a Benchmark has been configured, the benchmarking process is reduced to a handful of commands, making it a straightforward task for users. Once the results are obtained, the evaluation can be performed. At the moment, this is done by other downstream tools, such as a spreadsheet, although there is future work planned (described below) to interpret the results as well. Also, the

Run #	Tool	Runtime (Sec)	Memory (GB)
1	lofreq_indelqual	154	2.759
2	lofreq_indelqual	156	2.759
2	samtools_stats	40	0.005
...more results...			

TABLE I

EXAMPLE OUTPUT GENERATED BY THE `ABM history summarize` COMMAND, ALTHOUGH HEAVILY CONDENSED TO FIT THE PAPER FORMAT. THE OUTPUT OF THIS COMMAND ALLOWS A USER TO EASILY GET A IDEA OF RUNTIME CHARACTERISTICS OF INDIVIDUAL TOOLS COMPRISING A WORKFLOW. THE INTENT IS TO USE THIS DATA IN DOWNSTREAM TOOLS FOR FURTHER ANALYSIS AND VISUALIZATION.

next section shows an example of how short scripts can be used to aggregate and interpret the collected data.

B. Monitor Workflow Performance with Continuous Integration

Galaxy has sophisticated workflow capabilities with complex control structures, such as conditionals, dataset collections, and sub-workflows. These features are exposed via an accessible graphical editor, making it straightforward to develop sophisticated workflows. In addition, there are nearly 10,000 tools available in the Galaxy ecosystem, often offering several choices for accomplishing a given step of the data analysis process. As a consequence, design decisions and tool choice may have impact on workflow performance and runtime characteristics. As workflow developers interact with this increasingly complex system, there is a growing need to regularly evaluate and compare performance of different workflow builds. Ideally, this evaluation is part of the development and publishing life cycle.

Here we provide template GitHub repository with a GitHub Action that leverages ABM and allows a workflow developer to easily run workflow benchmarks and collect performance data (<https://github.com/SchatzLabJHU/abm-action>). The GitHub Action (shown in **Fig. 5**) will upload a given workflow and test data on the specified Galaxy servers, monitor its execution, collect the resulting performance data, and deposit the data in the repository. The Action can be defined to automatically run on each commit or pull request, making it a seamless and integral part of workflow development process. The collected performance data is visualized in the repository as default preliminary analysis while additional evaluation is certainly possible in downstream tools.

To start using this capability, anyone can add the action to a GitHub workflow, do a one-time configuration to supply the Galaxy API keys, and update a link to the workflow file and its input data. Subsequently, every update to the workflow file will yield a performance benchmark data point allowing easy evaluation of any performance changes.

C. Estimate Cloud Costs

The third use case showcases ABM's full capabilities in identifying the most desirable resource configurations for a given workload, going beyond benchmarking existing servers or ensuring workflow operability. ABM can reconfigure

```

- name: Test a workflow with ABM
  uses: SchatzLabJHU/abm-action@v1
  with:
    org-api-key: ${ secrets.ORG_API_KEY }
    histories-path: histories.yml
    workflows-path: workflows.yml
    benchmarks-file-path: benchmarks/vc.yml
    experiments-file-path: experiments/vc.yml

```

Fig. 5. GitHub Action used for Continuous Integration testing of a workflow.

Galaxy to explore how configuration changes impact workload performance. We leveraged this capability to benchmark cloud resources across tool/resource configurations to estimate workload costs on commercial cloud providers [1]. Cost estimation is invaluable for scientists considering cloud adoption, where cost uncertainty remains a major hurdle.

To identify desirable resource configurations and estimate the costs, we performed a number of experiments to measure the performance of several workflows across three dimensions: input data size, number of CPU cores allocated, and amount of memory allocated for a tool. In addition to all the benchmarking steps already described above, this use case requires Galaxy to be reconfigured for each distinct benchmark. Changes include updating Galaxy’s configurations to specify desired amount of resources for given tools and restarting necessary processes. Because these are system-level changes, this mode of ABM works only on Galaxy servers deployed on Kubernetes and using the Galaxy Helm chart [5]. Kubernetes offers a reliable mechanism for performing such changes in an automated fashion and is hence the reason why ABM only supports cluster changes for Kubernetes deployments.

To run such evaluation, in addition to defining an ABM Experiment, such as the one in in **Fig. 2**, it is also necessary to define desired job configurations as part of the Experiment:

```

job_configs:
  - 8x32
  - 32x64

```

Each of these configurations maps to a file that contains necessary rules indicating how many resources should be allocated for a given tool (e.g., <https://github.com/ksuderman/Benchmarks/blob/master/rnaseq/rules/8x32.yml>). Behind the scenes, ABM issues `kubectl` and `helm` commands to make the necessary cluster changes, updating the Galaxy deployment, and then instantiating the suitable workload. One thing to keep in mind that ABM will not scale the underlying cluster, which needs to have adequate resources to accommodate desired job configurations defined in the Experiment. In this mode, ABM can also install any missing tools in Galaxy, further automating the benchmarking process for newly created or temporary Galaxy deployments.

IV. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

A systematic approach to collecting benchmarking data is crucial for meaningful performance evaluation. The ABM tool streamlines this process with its well-defined, reproducible,

and shareable benchmarking configurations. This allows users from various backgrounds to easily evaluate their workloads. Our use cases validate ABM’s capabilities and demonstrate its support for different user personas.

One of the most impactful lessons from working with ABM is the importance of thoughtful benchmarking design. While ABM’s design capabilities enable quick execution of numerous jobs and collection of extensive runtime data, this can overwhelm users and produce noisy results. It is essential to focus on the specific goals of the evaluation and design compact experiments that test clear hypotheses, rather than amassing large volumes of data without direction.

ABM enhances users’ ability to understand correlations between different configuration options, such as resource requirements relative to input data size. Despite its current automation capabilities, manually collecting, organizing, and interpreting the resulting data can still be challenging. To address this, we plan to develop a hosted ABM service. This service will allow users to upload an Experiment configuration and ABM will automatically run the necessary workloads, generating a summary report that highlights key findings.

In conclusion, ABM provides a powerful tool for systematic and reproducible performance evaluation of Galaxy workloads, enabling users to optimize their workflows. Our future enhancements aim to further simplify the benchmarking process, making it more accessible and informative for users.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

We would like to thank the Galaxy Community for their contributions to the platform. This work was supported, in part, by NIH awards U24HG010263, U24HG006620, and R03CA272952 as well as NSF award 2005506.

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